

**Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering
Institute of Chemical and Environmental Engineering
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava**

PROCEEDINGS

37th International Conference of Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering

**Hotel Hutník
Tatranské Matliare, Slovakia
May 24 – 28, 2010**

Editor: J. Markoš

ISBN 978-80-227-3290-1

Variny, M., Mierka, O.: Lowering of the steam exergetic cost by the application of advanced gas turbines in an industrial company in slovakia, Editor: Markoš, J., In *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference of Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering*, Tatranské Matliare, Slovakia, 1104–1118, 2010.

LOWERING OF THE STEAM EXERGETIC COST BY THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED GAS TURBINES IN AN INDUSTRIAL COMPANY IN SLOVAKIA

Miroslav Variny, Otto Mierka Sr.

*Ústav chemického a environmentálneho inžinierstva FCHPT STU, Radlinského 9
812 37 Bratislava 1, phone number +421259325247, fax number +421252496920, email:
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk, otto.mierka@stuba.sk*

Keywords: heat and steam balance, exergy, ancillary services, fuel consumption

Introduction

The idea of increasing the efficiency of the energetic media production by the development and application of new technologies is embedded both in European [1,2] and Slovak legislation [3-6] as well as in various national strategic documents, like [7]. This legislation generally aims at renewing/revamping the older power plants and the industrial and municipal central heating and power plants. The employed means [5,6] include penalizing of the companies that fail to meet the increasing limits for the efficiency of the energetic media production and the financial support for the high efficient cogeneration units in terms of the fix electricity price [8], well above the market one. In order to prove a proposed solution to be efficient enough to receive the support, correct technical calculations are needed. Economic considerations are inevitable and vital to the project to attract (or, in the worse case to scary of) the investors. Technical and economical balances may be calculated with various degrees of complexity, beginning with semi empiric calculations based on the personal experience [9,10], through detailed balances of production units [11-14], ending with complex models [15-19] requiring much time and skill in programming. The theory of the exergetic cost, formed by Valero [19], together with later exergoeconomic considerations [20,21], is an appropriate tool for assessing both the technical and economic point of view of some project. Bearing all this in mind, we decided to apply the principles of the exergoeconomical analysis on a project in a large industrial central heating and power plant in a paper mill in Slovakia, aimed at revamping the existing obsolete combined cycle power plant (CCPP) by commissioning an additional new gas turbine and a heat recovery steam generator (HRSG). Such solution is generally known to be highly efficient in standard applications [15,22], thus we examined this thesis under less standard situation, since there is usually a plenty of low cost heat in the mentioned industry type. The technical part of the study includes the description of the actual situation, the choosing of suitable gas turbines, correcting their operational parameters with respect to local climatic conditions and calculating steam outputs of the HRSGs under full load and part load operation. Then, the energetic media production is estimated throughout the year, with respect to part load operation possibility. Afterwards, economic calculations give the fix costs for various alternatives and finally estimate individual project economies. Then the sensitivity analysis is conducted and finally the exergoeconomic analysis is employed for various project alternatives, to reliably distribute fix and variable exergoeconomic costs between produced steam and electricity. Considering the extent of results, the authors presented a part of it in the conference "Power Engineering 2010" held in Tatranske Matliare from the 18th to 20th of May and in this contribution, just some important related

figures and facts are reviewed, allowing in this contribution more accent on the exergoeconomic analysis.

Actual state description

The existing central heat and power plant can be separated into three more or less independent blocks – one of them is an obsolete CCPP, formed by two 17 MW gas turbines, two single-pressure (6.2 MPa , 440 °C) HRSGs equipped with a hot water section and a backpressure steam turbine (14 MW, oversized, used to provide tertiary frequency regulation – TRV+). A scheme of the mentioned CCPP can be seen in the **figure 1**.

Figure 1 Scheme of the existing CCPP

The reason for calling the given CCPP ‘obsolete’ stems, beside its advanced age, in the large internal heat consumption for steam injections and in the moderate electric efficiency of the gas turbines, reaching a maximum of 33 %. At full load, the gas turbines produce 33 MW of electricity; consume 105 MW in natural gas and 26 tones per hour (t/h) steam injections of totally 56 t/h steam raised in the HRSGs. The steam turbine produces some 1.5 MW of electricity. At a 67 % load, which corresponds to maximal ancillary services provisioning, the gas turbines produce 22 MW of electricity, consume 80 MW in natural gas (corresponding to 27.5 % gas turbine electric efficiency) and 9 t/h steam out of totally 40 t/h raised in the HRSGs. The steam turbine output is the same as at the GT full load. Taken together, the overall CCPP efficiency (based on the lower heating value of the natural gas) does not exceed some 65 to 70 %. There is an apparent difference between this CCPP and the modern CCPPs, employing the gas turbines with the electric efficiencies near or above 40 % and dry low NO_x emissions systems reducing the internal heat consumption, allowing the overall efficiency to exceed 80 to 85 %. The only problem of such gas turbines is their decreasing output and efficiency with the increasing ambient temperature, whereas the gas turbines with the steam injections can reach the same maximum output in the winter as well as in the summer. The HRSGs are equipped with the supplementary firing, which is used during the winter to

raise additional steam for the heating with an efficiency exceeding 100 % [13,24]. The CCPP products are the electricity and the backpressure 0.6 MPa steam.

The remaining two blocks are common Rankine cycle units, combusting industrial by-products and recycling chemicals used for the pulp production by the Kraft process. The industrial by-product is a low calorific low cost fuel, which may be either combusted in the industry or sold to some customers. Since the combustion of this fuel keeps the steam demand and steam production balanced, the commissioning of a new gas turbine (GT) and a HRSG decreases its consumption. Taken together, the additional steam production in the new HRSG results a great deal in cheap fuel savings (and just in winter in natural gas savings), which significantly deteriorates the project economy. The Rankine units' products are electricity; the extraction 1.3 MPa steam and the backpressure 0.6 MPa steam.

Revamp possibilities

As already mentioned above, we sought gas turbines, available on the market, suitable for upgrading the existing CCPP. Considering the electric balance if the industry, we decided to select the gas turbines in the 15 to 20 MW range and in the 30 MW range. **Table 1 a,b** gives an overview of the selected gas turbines in both output ranges; their operational parameters being slightly changed to reflect the local climatic conditions. For the smaller gas turbines we employed a single pressure HRSG with a hot water section and the stack temperature of 130 °C; for the bigger ones we employed a dual pressure HRSG (6.2 MPa, 440 °C; 1.3 MPa , 255 °C) together with a hot water section and the stack temperature of 100 °C. 1.3 MPa steam is produced exclusively in the Rankine units today's. Steam production in the HRSGs was calculated via the procedure described in [23], using well known pinch technique and a combination of material and heat balances.

Gas turbine	L20A [25]	PGT 20 [26]	LM2500 [26]	Titan 250 [27]
Manufacturer	Kawasaki Heavy Industries	General Electric	General Electric	Turbomach
Electric output, MW	17.1	16.6	20.8	20.7
Electric efficiency, %	32.0	33.4	36.1	37.2
Flue gas temperature, °C	545	475	532	468
Produced 6,2 MPa steam, t/h	29.1	22.2	31.5	23.2
Saved 0.6 MPa steam utilizing the hot water section, t/h	7.5	10.4	9.1	11.6

Table 1a Full load ISO operational parameters of the selected gas turbines in the 15 to 20 MW output range.

In order to ensure the production of 440 °C high pressure steam in HRSGs, gas turbines with flue gas temperature lower than 460 °C were excluded from our study. We considered two operational modes in the 15 to 20 MW range gas turbines: full load operation with no AS provisioning, or 67 % load operation with maximum AS provisioning [13,14]. Based upon our experience with gas turbine and HRSG operational modes as well as upon obtained data [28], we were able to estimate the change in corresponding operational parameters when operating at 67 % load: GT electric efficiency lowers to 90 % of the full load value, high pressure steam production

lowers to 67 % of the full load value and 0.6 MPa steam saving shrinks to 75 % of the full load value.

Gas turbine	PGT 25+ [26]	LM2500+ [29]	RB211 6761 [30]	SGT-700 [31]
Manufacturer	General Electric	General Electric	Rolls Royce	Siemens
Electric output, MW	28.7	29.0	30.2	29.6
Electric efficiency, %	37.6	38.7	37.1	34.6
Flue gas temperature, °C	500	516	505	528
Produced 6.2 MPa steam, t/h	34.1	37.7	38.9	43.1
Produced 1.3 MPa steam, t/h	7.7	7.4	8.4	7.7
Saved 0.6 MPa steam utilizing the hot water section, t/h	8.7	8.7	9.6	9.1

Table 1b Full load ISO operational parameters of the selected gas turbines in the 30 MW output range.

The GT flue gas temperature above 460 °C was required in the 30 MW range as well. In this output range we similarly consider two operational modes: full load operation and 67 % operation. However, in the case of full load operation, the old CCPP was set out of operation (except the steam turbine), since the electricity production would exceed its total consumption in the given industry by the simultaneous operation of both the old and new CCPP parts. The new HRSG needed to be equipped with the supplementary firing in order to balance the steam production and consumption during winter. There was no need to account with supplementary firing in the maximal AS provisioning operational mode, considering the overall increase in steam production by the new GT and HRSG operation. At 67 % load, we considered the decrease of operational parameters to following values: GT electric efficiency lowers to 92 % of the full load value; the decrease in high pressure steam production and 0.6 MPa steam saving is the same as in the 15 to 20 MW GT output range and finally the 1.3 MPa steam production shrinks to 90 % of the full load value. All these changes in both the 15 to 20 and the 30 MW output range result from the lowered GT flue gas temperature and a less significant mass flow decrease, combined with the changed heat transfer conditions in the HRSG. In summer, we accounted with further decrease in the GT and HRSG operational parameters at both the full load and the 67 % load, thus incorporating the negative influence of the elevated ambient temperature on the GT operation in the calculation model.

Modeling the central heat and power plant

For the sake of the further calculations, we divided the operation of the central heat and power plant into three operational modes, according to the season of the year.

1. Winter operation: Both Rankine units operate at full load with maximal backpressure and minimal steam condensation electricity production. The CCPP operates at 67 % load; the supplementary firing in the HRSGs is utilized. Natural gas consumption for supplementary firing is 23.1 MW and the steam mass flow raised by the supplementary firing is 30 t/h. The slope of the CCPP steam turbine consumption characteristics is 6.9 tones of steam per MWh (t/MWh) of electric energy and the slope of the condensing steam turbine characteristics in the Rankine units (this condensing steam turbine utilizes the excess of the 0.6 MPa steam) is 6.7 t/MWh. Each increase of

the steam production in the CCPP results in the lowering of supplementary firing natural gas consumption. Eventually, if the steam production increase exceeds 30 t/h, supplementary firing is switched off and there is an increase in the electricity production on the CCPP steam turbine. Furthermore, the excess steam can be utilized in the condensing steam turbine as well, boosting the increase in the electricity production.

2. Spring and autumn operation: Both Rankine units operate at full load with maximal backpressure and moderate steam condensation electricity production (there is free capacity of 30 t/h in the steam condensing turbine). The CCPP operates at 67 % load; the supplementary firing in the HRSGs is no longer utilized. Each increase in the steam production in the CCPP results in the increased backpressure electricity production and, consequently, in the increased steam condensing electricity production. Eventually, if the steam production increases by more than 35 t/h (includes the increased internal steam consumption for the condensate heating and deaeration), there is excess steam in the industry. The excess 0.6 MPa steam may be either vented into the atmosphere, or, to restore the steam balance, one of the boilers in the Rankine units lowers its steam output. On the one hand, it means a fuel saving (a cheap fuel), but on the other one, it results in decreased backpressure electricity production in the Rankine units. The corresponding slope of the backpressure steam turbine characteristics is 8 t/MWh.

3. Summer operation: Both Rankine units operate at full load with maximal backpressure and maximal steam condensation electricity production. The CCPP operates at 67 % load; the supplementary firing in the HRSGs is not utilized. Each steam production increase in the CCPP results in the increase of the backpressure electricity production in the CCPP, but consequently in the decrease of the backpressure electricity production in the Rankine units and in the saving of the cheap fuel for the Rankine unit steam boiler. Continuous steam venting into the atmosphere is not allowed.

By calculating electricity production, natural gas consumption and steam balances for each season of the year, we obtained **table 2 a,b**.

Gas turbine	L20A	PGT 20	LM2500	Titan 250
Load	67 %			
The increase in the electricity production *, GWh	103.1	97.8	125.1	119.7
The increase in NG consumption, GWh	262.5	251.4	286.9	283.9
Fuel savings in the Rankine units, GWh	38.8	36.2	44.4	39.6
Marginal electric efficiency, %	42.4	41.9	47.3	45.3
Load	100 %			
The increase in the electricity production, GWh	162.1	147.5	193.6	183.3
The increase in NG consumption, GWh	371.7	339.9	406.9	389.7
Fuel savings in the Rankine units, GWh	68.6	61.4	87.0	65.6
Marginal electric efficiency, %	48.0	47.7	53.3	51.4

Table 2a The yearly change in the energetic media consumption and production by employing GTs in the range 15 to 20 MW. * - a proportional 5 % increase in internal electricity consumption is included

Gas turbine	PGT 25+	LM2500+	RB211 6761	SGT-700
Load		67 %		
The increase in the electricity production, GWh*	181.0	186.4	197.8	194.7
The increase in NG consumption, GWh	381.7	375.7	426.4	446.2
Fuel savings in the Rankine units, GWh	58.8	66.9	78.8	86.8
Marginal electric efficiency, %	51.4	54.5	51.1	48.3
Load		100 %		
The increase in the electricity production, GWh	-40.8	-36.0	-24.5	-25.6
The increase in NG consumption, GWh	-295.5	-312.0	-266.0	-238.0
Fuel savings in the Rankine units, GWh	3.4	8.4	14.2	18.0
Marginal electric efficiency, %	–	–	–	–

Table 2b The yearly change in the energetic media consumption and production by employing GTs in the 30 MW range. * - a proportional 5 % increase in internal electricity consumption is included

Marginal electric efficiency [18] of each individual alternative was calculated by following equation:

$$\eta_{el,marg} = \frac{\Delta P_{el}}{\Delta P_{NG} - 0.5 \cdot S_F} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

Meaning of used symbol is as follows: $\eta_{el,marg}$ - marginal electric efficiency; ΔP_{el} - increase in electric output of the central heating and power station; ΔP_{NG} - increase in heat input in the NG (based on lower heating value); S_F – savings of the cheap fuel in the Rankine units. The coefficient 0.5 may perhaps be considered as an ad-hoc number, but it accounts for the fact that the saved cheap fuel may be sold to external consumers, where it replaces NG. However, it is a low calorific fuel and the heat production efficiency using this fuel is lower than that of NG. Furthermore, we included losses through transportation and since we do not have any precise evidence of how far the fuel is being transported and to what extent it replaces the natural gas, we had to accommodate ourselves with estimation and took the value 0.5 as rational. The variation of the coefficient in the range ± 0.5 influences the marginal electric efficiency by ± 4 to ± 5 % and must thus be considered as an important unknown variable.

As one can recognize, the marginal electric efficiencies in the 67 % load operation vary in a wide range from 42 % in the least efficient unit to over 54 % in the most efficient one. By the comparison of the electric efficiencies of the gas turbines and the steam mass flows produced in the HRSGs (e.g. the degree of utilization of the waste heat energy of the flue gases in the HRSGs) it is apparent that the values of the gas turbines electric efficiencies play the more important role in the final marginal electric efficiency. The situation may have been more balanced if there was either free steam condensing capacity in summer, or the fuel combusted in the Rankine units would be more valuable (like NG). The first possibility may have resulted in an approximately 1 % increase of the marginal electric efficiency and the second one would correspond to the situation described above (e.g. increase of the marginal electric efficiency by 4 to 5 %). However, the obtained values of the

marginal electric efficiencies more or less correspond to those described in other papers [15,18,22] and justify the application of such solutions in the industry from the technical point of view.

The marginal electric efficiencies in the 100 % load operation are significantly higher than those in the 67 % load operation which again stems from both higher gas turbine electric efficiencies and higher degree of the flue gas waste heat utilization in the HRSGs. In the case of the 30 MW gas turbines range, marginal electric efficiencies could not be estimated using the definition (1) since it can not accommodate a situation in which a larger, less efficient unit (e.g. the old GTs and HRSGs) are replaced by a somewhat smaller and more efficient one. In order to be able to calculate the marginal electric efficiencies in those alternatives, we would have to suppose the old CCPP parts either to stay in operation (which would mean a part of the produced electricity being sold to external grid – this is not acceptable from the economical point of view) or to had already been decommissioned prior to this study.

Economic considerations

Following the technical calculation, we carried out a simplified economic analysis as well. To calculate the fix costs, we assumed following figures: Cost of installed GT in the range 15 to 20 MW equal to 750 €/kW_{ISO output} and in the 30 MW range equal to 700 €/kW_{ISO output}. The cost of the installed HRSG was calculated using the modified equation from [22]:

$$C_{HRSG} [\text{thousands U.S.}\$] = 771,5 \cdot \left(Q_{HRSG}^* [MW] \right)^{0,667} \quad (2)$$

with the following meaning of used symbols: C_{HRSG} – cost of installed HRSG; Q_{HRSG}^* - heat output of HRSG, where the hot water section output was included with the coefficient 0.5 to distinguish between the high pressure steam generation and the hot water production. The installation cost of the supplementary firing was assumed to reach one million dollars [28]. To carry out all calculations in euros, we assumed the exchange course €/\\$ = 1.4. Furthermore we assumed a 12-year linear depreciation; the O&M costs reaching each year 10 % of the total installed cost and the insurance cost yearly 2 % on the same basis. The investment costs were assumed to be available via a 20-year loan with an interest rate of 6 % p.a. Other payments include the salaries for three operators and one manager.

The applied costs of the energetic media were as follows: cost of electricity – 90 €/MWh, cost of NG – 27 €/MWh, cost of cheap fuel – 11 €/MWh. To see the structure of the incomes from the AS provisioning, please consult [23] and to learn more about the AS generally and especially in Slovakia, please consult [15, 32-36].

By applying all these considerations to the results of the technical calculations, we obtained financial data presented in **table 3 a,b**. Surprisingly both 67 % and 100 % operations yield similar results which mean that the lower efficiencies in the 67 % operation (and thus lower incomes from produced electricity and higher NG costs) were more or less balanced by the incomes from the AS provisioning. Considering the increasing number of potential AS providers in Slovakia combined with the projects of building several large CCPPs in Slovakia leads us to extensive doubts about the ability of such (comparatively small) industrial CCPP being able to provide AS in an economically feasible way. Obviously, the full load operation becomes far more probable or even necessary in the near or mid-term future. However, none of the available solutions can guarantee a satisfactory project economics – in order to obtain a simple payback time of ten years, the resulting project economics would have to reach at least 2 million euros per year, considering the current energetic

media costs. In other words, all these projects may improve their economics only after being fully depreciated (e.g. after 12 years) which is not acceptable.

Gas turbine	L20A		PGT20		LM2500		Titan 250	
Load, %	67	100	67	100	67	100	67	100
Fix costs, mil. € / year	5.36	5.36	5.10	5.10	6.34	6.34	6.06	6.06
Income from produced electricity, mil. € / year	9.28	14.59	8.80	13.28	11.26	17.42	10.77	16.50
Income from AS provisioning, mil. € / year	2.89	0	2.95	0	3.42	0	3.52	0
Cheap fuel savings, mil. € / year	0.43	0.75	0.40	0.68	0.49	0.96	0.44	0.72
Natural gas cost, mil. € / year	7.09	10.04	6.79	9.18	7.75	10.99	7.67	10.52
Project economics before taxing, mil. € / year	+0.15	-0.06	+0.26	-0.32	+1.08	+1.05	+1.00	+0.64

Table 3a Individual project economics for the 15 to 20 MW range GTs.

Gas turbine	PGT 25+		LM2500+		RB211 6761		SGT-700	
Load, %	67	100	67	100	67	100	67	100
Fix costs, mil. € / year*	7.94	4.62	8.07	4.76	8.39	5.08	8.36	5.05
Income from produced electricity, mil. € / year	16.29	-3.67	16.78	-3.24	17.80	-2.21	17.52	-2.30
Income from AS provisioning, mil. € / year	4.99	0	4.93	0	4.93	0	4.90	0
Cheap fuel savings, mil. € / year	0.65	0.03	0.74	0.09	0.87	0.16	0.95	0.20
Natural gas cost, mil. € / year	10.31	-7.98	10.14	-8.42	11.51	-7.18	12.05	-6.43
Project economics before taxing, mil. € / year	+3.68	-0.28	+4.24	+0.51	+3.70	+0.05	+2.96	-0.72

Table 3b Individual project economics for the 30 MW range GTs. * - includes an estimate of 3.6 mil. €/year fix costs savings by the decommissioning of the old CCPP parts in the 100 % load alternatives.

By comparing figures given in **table 3a** and **table 3b**, one again sees that the AS provisioning is at present the only possibility to ensure good project economics. The corresponding incomes before taxing exceeding 3 million euros per year mean the simple payback period to be shorter than 10 years. The full load operation results are really interesting, since the only factor they are sensitive to is the NG price. But to guarantee satisfactory project economics, the NG price would have to rise to at least 40 €/MWh and stay as high for several years. In that case, however, one would have to decompose the project economics between the old CCPP parts decommissioning and the new GT and HRSG commissioning to see whether to invest in the new CCPP parts or to accept the decrease of electricity production. As a conclusion of these results, the investment in the new GTs and HRSGs is quite risky despite their excellent technical parameters. At this point, the industry should seek some sort of financial support either from the Slovak Republic or from the European Union via the structural funds. Moreover, the Slovak Republic may perhaps have to reconsider its

energetic security priorities and to strengthen the support of highly efficient distributed power generation.

We carried out the sensitivity analysis as well; please consult [23] to see the detailed results. Its outcomes support our statements about the risky and possibly unpleasant outcome of such investment without some sort of financial support.

Exergoeconomic analysis – theoretical background

In contrast to standard cost analysis in combined heat and power production, the exergoeconomic analysis distributes the costs incurred by the production process according to exergetic flows and not the energetic ones. Since exergy is understood as that portion of energy that can (theoretically, by the Carnot cycle) be transformed to the useful work, this means of product costing may solve some present problems in the cost distribution process. If we define the reference state by its specific enthalpy h_o , specific entropy s_o and thermodynamic temperature T_o , we can calculate the specific exergy b of a physical stream, characterized by its specific enthalpy h and specific entropy s as (3):

$$b = h - h_o - T_o \cdot (s - s_o) \quad (3)$$

For an ideal gas or gas mixture, characterized by its pressure p , molar mass M and molar heat capacity in the form $c_p(T)$, following equation can be used to calculate its specific exergy as:

$$b = h - T_o \cdot s = \left[\int_{T_o}^T c_p(T) \cdot dT - T_o \cdot \int_{T_o}^T \frac{c_p(T)}{T} \cdot dT + R \cdot T_o \ln \left(\frac{p}{p_o} \right) \right] \cdot \frac{1}{M} \quad (4)$$

In this case we arbitrarily set the specific enthalpy and the specific entropy of the reference state equal to zero and disregarded the exergy change by gas mixing [32].

For a process unit with i inlet streams and j outlet streams following equation holds true:

$$\sum_i^* B_i \geq \sum_j^* B_j \quad (5)$$

This means that the exergy is not a conservative quantity; the equality sign is valid only for reversible (and thus theoretical) process. The real processes like the combustion, the heat transfer, the expansion and compression, the pressure losses and many others are inherently irreversible.

The unit exergetic cost k_j of process outlet stream can be calculated by employing the equations (3-5) as (6):

$$k_j = \sum_i^* B_i / \sum_j^* B_j = 1/\eta_b \quad (6)$$

From (6) we see that in real processes k_j adopts values greater than unity and is equal to the reverse value of the process exergetic efficiency. According to the unit exergetic cost computation rules [19], if a process has several outlet streams, their formation processes are indistinguishable and therefore they have the same unit exergetic cost. This rule can be applied for example to a backpressure steam turbine, which has two product streams – electric energy and backpressure steam.

The meaning of unit exergetic cost is that if multiplied by the process stream exergy, it gives the exergy of the fuel (e.g. exergetic input) which had to be consumed in order to produce this stream.

Formally the same approach may then be used in costing analysis. The fuel for a production unit (like natural gas or coal or other fuel) with a known unit price c_F (which can be expressed either

on mass, molar or volume basis), forms the input cost for a process. The cost is conservative quantity, therefore the following holds true:

$$\sum_i C_i + E_x = \sum_j C_j \quad (7)$$

The equation states that the sum of product costs C_j is equal to the sum of input costs C_i increased by the externalities. The externalities include for example the operation and maintenance costs (O&M), depreciations, insurance payments, loan payments, personal costs and other.

Knowing the unit j -th stream cost c_j (for example in €/kg) and its specific exergy b_j (in kJ/kg), a unit exergoeconomic cost k_j^* can be assigned to this stream (8):

$$k_j^* = c_j / b_j \text{ [eur/kJ]} \quad (8)$$

Thus, with the help of the equations (3-8), one can conduct the costing analysis as follows (9):

$$\sum_i k_i^* B_i + E_x = \sum_j k_j^* B_j \quad (9)$$

In this equation, the unit exergoeconomic costs of the input streams are known and that of the output streams are unknown. The same computation rules can be applied like those for unit exergetic cost calculation.

From the above theoretical background it is apparent that in order to conduct the exergoeconomic analysis correctly, one needs accurate data about the process streams (T , p , h , s , mass flows ...) as well as about the process itself (electric and heat efficiencies, steam turbine adiabatic expansion efficiency...) and its economics (mainly fuel prices and externalities). This is the reason why we dealt a lot with technical calculations, namely with the heat and mass balances and with the fix costs calculations.

Exergoeconomic analysis - computation

The reference state chosen for the calculation of the exergies of the flue gases was characterized through: $T_0 = 298.15$ K, $p_0 = 100.5$ kPa. We arbitrarily assigned zero enthalpy and entropy value to this reference state, regardless of the chemical composition of the flue gases [37]. For the calculation of steam and water exergies, we chose following reference state: $T_0 = 298.15$ K, boiling water; this reference state yields $h_0 = 104.8$ kJ/kg and $s_0 = 0.367$ kJ/kg. The flue gases exiting the gas turbines were supposed to have the pressure $p = 102$ kPa. The flue gases exiting the HRSG are useless for heat and power generation, thus their exergy content was disregarded for the sake of the exergoeconomic analysis. The flue gas composition was set to (% mol.): $N_2 - 75.3$, $O_2 - 12.5$, $CO_2 - 3.7$, $H_2O - 8.5$ which corresponds to the average flue gas composition exiting a modern gas turbine [28]. The ambient temperature was set to 25 °C, which allowed us to neglect the combustion air exergy as well.

The specific chemical exergy of the natural gas b_{NG} was calculated via (10) [38]:

$$b_{NG} = \phi \cdot LHV \quad (10)$$

In (10) the coefficient Φ was set equal to 1.057 [38] and LHV means lower heating value of the natural gas set to be 99 % of the lower heating value of pure methane, according to [39]. The physical exergy of the natural gas entering the GT was neglected, since its contribution to the total NG exergy is very small.

Figure 2 The energetic media unit exergetic costs evolution for various configurations at 67 % load. Light blue – electricity and flue gases from the GTs; orange – steam and hot water exiting the HRSG; green – electric energy and 0.6 MPa steam from the steam turbine.

Figure 3 The energetic media exergoeconomic costs evolution for various configurations at 67 % load. Light grey – the cost of the electricity produced by the GT; light orange – the mixed cost of the electricity produced by the steam turbine; blue – the mixed cost of the total produced electricity.

The results of both exergetic and exergoeconomic analysis are shown in the **figures 2-5**. Considering the unit exergetic cost of CCPP products in the figures 2 and 4, which is directly related to the respective exergetic and electric efficiencies, one generally distinguishes three groups of values. The largest unit exergetic cost of produced 0.6 MPa steam is characteristic for the old CCPP parts, which corresponds with their moderate electric and exergetic efficiencies. Somewhat lower steam unit exergetic costs are seen in the 15 to 20 MW GT range, which is a result of the

improvement achieved in steam and electricity production efficiency by incorporating a new GT and a HRSG into the existing CCPP. The lowest steam unit exergetic costs are characteristic for the GTs in the 30 MW ranges, which is mainly caused by their higher electric efficiency, by the lower internal steam consumption and by the dual pressure design of the HRSGs. As a general conclusion, the steam unit exergetic cost can truly be lowered by revamping the existing somewhat obsolete CCPP, regardless if operated at the 67 % load or at the full load.

Figure 4 The energetic media unit exergetic costs evolution for various configurations at 100 % load. Light blue – electricity and flue gases from the GTs; orange – steam and hot water exiting the HRSG; green – electric energy and 0.6 MPa steam from the steam turbine

Figure 5 The energetic media exergoeconomic costs evolution for various configurations at 100 % load. Light grey – the cost of the electricity produced by the GT; light orange – the mixed cost of the electricity produced by the steam turbine; blue – the mixed cost of the total produced electricity.

However, the pure thermodynamic analysis of the given central heating and power plant does not tell us anything about the costs of the produced energetic media. Considering the electric efficiencies supremacy of the studied gas turbines over the older ones, one becomes aware of possibly lower fuel costs and consequently of possibly lower variable production cost of the electricity. Unfortunately, this positive fact is nearly outweighed by much higher fix production cost of the electricity. As can be recognized in the **figures 3,5**, it results in either increased electricity exergoeconomic cost and comparatively steady 0.6 MPa steam exergoeconomic cost (**figure 3**; GTs operated at the 67 % load), or in lower or steady electricity exergoeconomic cost and lower steam exergoeconomic cost (**figure 5**, GTs operated at the full load). Consequently it must be concluded that the investment attractiveness of the new CCPP technologies is lowered by the expected increase in the fix costs mainly due to the amortization, the O&M costs and the loan payments and by the uncertainty about the future fuel and energy prices.

Conclusions

We consider the methodology of this extensive study as a possible concept for the evaluation of increased cogeneration potential possibilities in other Slovak industries, both from thermodynamic as well as from economical point of view. It was by chance that we chose to study the situation in an industry with a plenty of low cost low temperature heat, but its outcome is obvious in the marginal efficiencies of various alternatives ranging from 45 to 55 %. If such efficiency values are possible in that kind of industry, values over 60 % may be achieved in other types of industry, using more expensive and higher calorific fuels. In order to achieve such efficiency in a stand alone power plant (disregarding the transmission losses), much bigger power plant is needed. Siemens [40] and General Electric [41] report 60 % net electric efficiencies just in their recent 400 to 800 MW range CCPPs applying their latest gas turbine technologies and 16.5 MPa/565 °C steam parameters. Such power plant parameters can not be compared to the distributed electricity generation by the modest 20 to 40 MW power output increase proposed in our study. Thus, in this case a small solution can be as efficient as a large one and does certainly more contribute to the electricity grid security than a large power plant. Those facts are something of which the people dealing with Slovakia's future energetic security should be aware and should try to support such projects.

List of used symbols and abbreviations

AS	ancillary services	
CCPP	combined cycle power plant	
LHV	lower heating value	[kJ/m ³]
NG	natural gas	
O&M	operation & maintenance	
P _{el}	electric output	[kW, MW]
SRV	secondary frequency regulation	
TRV	tertiary reserve	
η	efficiency	

References

- [1] Directive of the European parliament 2001/77/ES.
- [2] Directive of the European parliament and Commission 2003/54/ES.

- [3] Zbierka zákonov č. **656/2004** zákon z 26.októbra 2004 o energetike a o zmene niektorých zákonov.
- [4] Zbierka zákonov č. **657/2004** zákon z 26. októbra 2004 o tepelnej energetike.
- [5] Zbierka zákonov č. **476/2008** zákon zo 4. novembra 2008 o efektívnosti pri používaní energie (zákon o energetickej efektívnosti) a o zmene a doplnení zákona č. 555/2005 Z. z. o energetickej hospodárnosti budov a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov v znení zákona č. 17/2007 Z. z.
- [6] Zbierka zákonov č. **309/2009** zákon z 19. júna 2009 o podpore obnoviteľných zdrojov energie a vysokoúčinnej kombinovanej výroby a o zmene a doplnení niektorých zákonov.
- [7] Návrh stratégie energetickej bezpečnosti Slovenskej Republiky - materiál z rokovania vlády 117/2008, 15.10.2008, 20. bod programu.
- [8] Výnos URSO č. 7/2009 z 9.9.2009, ktorým sa mení a dopĺňa výnos URSO č. 2/2008 z 28. júla 2008, ktorým sa ustanovuje regulácia cien v elektroenergetike v znení neskorších predpisov.
- [9] Dalsgård, H., Petersen, P., M., Qvale, B. (2002): Simplification of process integration studies in intermediate size industries. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol.43, 1393-1405.
- [10] Variny, M., Mierka, O. (2007): Steam expansion adiabatic efficiency analysis – a practical tool for steam turbine performance optimization. Sborník z 54. konferencie chemického a procesného inžinýrství CHISA 2007 (CD), Srní, Česká Republika, Október 2007, ISBN 80-86059-47-2, Prednáška.
- [11] Gebremedhin, A. (2003): The role of a paper mill in a merged district heating system. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol.23, 769-778.
- [12] Goršek, A., Glavič, P. (2003): Process integration of a steam turbine. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol.23, 1227-1234.
- [13] Variny, M., Mierka, O. (2009): Implementation of marginal quantities in management of cogeneration units operating in liberal market environment. *Proceedings of 36th International Conference of Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering (CD)*, Tatranské Matliare, Slovenská Republika, Máj 2009, ISBN 978-80-227-3072-3, Lecture.
- [14] Variny, M., Mierka, O. (2009): Improvement of part load efficiency of a combined cycle power plant provisioning ancillary services. *Applied Energy*, Vol.86, No.6, 888-894.
- [15] Battisti, E. et al. (2006): Economical considerations about combined cycle power plant controls in deregulated market. *Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, Vol.28, 284 -292.
- [16] Franco, A., Russo, A. (2002): Combined cycle plant efficiency increase based on the optimization of the heat recovery steam generator operating parameters. *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, Vol.41, 843-859.
- [17] Manninen, J., Zhu, X., X. (1998): Thermodynamic analysis and mathematical optimization of power plants. *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, Vol.22, 537-544.
- [18] Thorin, E., Brand, H., Weber, Ch. (2005): Long-term optimization of cogeneration systems in a competitive market environment. *Applied Energy*, Vol.81, 152-169.
- [19] Valero, A. et al. (2002): Structural theory and thermoeconomic diagnosis Part II: Application to an actual power plant. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol.43, 1519-1535.
- [20] Sue, D.-Ch., Chuang, Ch.-Ch. (2004): Engineering design and exergy analyses for combustion gas turbine based power generation system. *Energy*, Vol. 29, 1183-1205.
- [21] Zhang, Ch., et al.(2006): Exergetic cost analysis of a coal fired power plant based on structural theory of thermoeconomics. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol. 47, 817-843.
- [22] Carapelucci, R., Milazzo, A. (2007): Repowering combined cycle power plants by a modified STIG configuration. *Energy Conversion and Management*, Vol.48, 1590-1600.

[23] Variny, M., Mierka, O. (2010): The improvement in the efficiency of energetic media production in an industrial heating and power plant by the application of advanced combined cycle technologies. The conference Power Engineering 2010, Tatranské Matliare, Slovenská Republika, Máj 2010, Lecture (In Slovak).

[24] Pasha, A., Jolly, S. (1995): Combined cycle heat recovery steam generators optimum capabilities and selection criteria. *Heat Recovery & CHP*, Vol.15, No.2, 147-154.

[25] Technical parameters of the L20A gas turbine:
<http://www.kawasakigasturbines.com/products/index/view/id/6/>

[26] Informative catalogue about the General Electric gas turbines product range :
http://www.gepower.com/businesses/ge_oilandgas/en/downloads/gas_turb_cat.pdf

[27] Informative brochure of the Titan 250 gas turbine:
http://turbomach.cat.com/cda/files/1071134/7/TUR_Titan250.pdf

[28] Consultations and personal correspondence with cogeneration unit's producers and operators.

[29] Technical parameters of the LM2500+ gas turbine:
http://www.gepower.com/prod_serv/products/aero_turbines/en/downloads/lm2500.pdf

[30] Informative brochure of the RB211 gas turbine product range: http://www.rolls-royce.com/Images/fs_rb211_tcm92-6732.pdf

[31] Informative catalogue about the Siemens gas turbines product range:
http://www.energy.siemens.com/hq/pool/hq/power-generation/gas-turbines/downloads/Industrial%20Gas%20Turbines/E50001-G430-A100-V1-4A00_Gas%20Turbine_Broschuere_E_LR.pdf

[32] Cenové rozhodnutie URSO v oblasti Elektroenergetika, číslo 0013/2010/E zo dňa 21.10.2009 pre subjekt Slovenská elektrizačná prenosová sústava, a.s., Mlynské Nivy 59/A, 824 84 Bratislava

[33] Kristiansen, T. (2007): The Nordic approach to market-based provision of ancillary services. *Energy Policy*, Vol.35, 3681-3700.

[34] Müller, G., Rammerstorfer, M. (2008): A theoretical analysis of procurement auctions for tertiary control in Germany. *Energy Policy*, Vol.36, 2620-2627.

[35] Raineri, R., Ríos, S., Schiele, D. (2006): Technical and economic aspects of ancillary services markets in the electric power industry: an international comparison. *Energy Policy*, Vol.34, 1540-1555.

[36] Technical conditions for ancillary services provisioning in Slovakia :
<http://www.sepsas.sk/seps/TechnickePodmienky.asp?kod=281>

[37] Sanjay, Y., Singh, O., Prasad, B., N. (2007): Energy and exergy analysis of steam cooled reheat gas-steam combined cycle. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol. 27, 2779-2790.

[38] Kotas, T., J.: *The Exergy Method of Thermal Plant Analysis*. New York: Krieger, 1995.

[39] Informative natural gas composition in the year 2009 given by the natural gas distribution company SPP in Slovakia: <http://www.spp.sk/o-zemnom-plyne/emisie/>

[40] Informative brochure about Siemens's large gas turbines and CCPPs:
http://www.energy.siemens.com/hq/pool/hq/power-generation/gas-turbines/downloads/SGT_over_100MW.pdf

[41] Smith, R., W. et al: *Advanced technology power cycles*. Available at
http://gepower.com/prod_serv/products/tech_docs/en/downloads/ger3936a.pdf